

Research

Comparative Study on Automatic Fabric Cutting Machine and Straight Knife Cutting Machine

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Abstract: Development of any manufacturing industry highly depends on the employment of the latest technology and well trained manpower. Likewise, automation plays a significant role in every sector of modern industry including Textile. Textile industry is one of the fastest growing manufacturing industries of the new era all around the world where technological development of automated machineries can be seen in almost every section to maintain the better quality product. Higher production with greater efficiency, lower labor cost and minimized wastage percentage with better quality products in each section of production can lead one to the front line of the competitive market. Cutting section of this sector is a very important section where precise cutting with higher accuracy must be maintained to meet the lead time and on time shipment. In Bangladesh, most of the factories use semi-automatic machine to accomplish the cutting process. But with the increasing demand of automated technology, the automatic fabric cutting machine is also being used gradually in some factories because of the higher efficiency and reduced production time. In this paper, the cutting process for same fabric has been studied by using both semi-automatic and full-automatic machine to evaluate the various cutting parameters. This study helps to determine the effectiveness and usefulness of both machines from various perspective of production. The significance and viability of using automatic cutting machines have been reported to cope up with the evaluation of Industry 4.0.

Keywords: Automation; cutting machine; straight knife; industry 4.0

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1. Introduction

With the evaluation of Industry 4.0, industrial automation has been extensively adopted in all kinds of modern factories from electronics, medical, car manufacturing to garment and textile industries. This automation technology is, nowadays, followed not only for major assembly or parts fabrication but also to a wide range of applications. Consequently, there is an ongoing trend of using automatic cutting machines to cut fabrics in the textile and garment industries. Hence, cutting is the separation of a physical object, into two or more pieces, through the application of an acutely directed force [1]. In a garment section, there are several functions in a cutting section such as fabric spreading, cutting, numbering and bundling of cut panels. Fabric cutting is the second irreversible process of garment

manufacturing after knitting and weaving where a fabric layer is converted into cut parts. Multiple layers of fabric are cut either by reciprocating knife action, unidirectional knife action or guillotine action [2]. Subsequently different types of cutting machines and equipment are available for cutting fabrics and machines that are used as per requirement and production volume [3].

Cutting can be performed manually using powered knives or by computer-controlled system [4]. In the past, scissors were used for fabric or cloth cutting. Then, semi-automatic machines were introduced. Nowadays, technological innovations and developments have led to the introduction of automation in the production processes. The most universally used machine for multiple layer cutting is a straight knife which works on the principle of a vertically reciprocating knife [2]. The elements of a straight knife consist of a base plate, usually on rollers for ease of movement, a straight, vertical blade with varying edge characteristics and an electric motor above it, a handle for the cutter to direct the blade, and a sharpening device [5]. The cost of this machine is comparatively cheaper than other cutting machines. Most importantly, fabric can be cut from any angle [6]. Hence this cutting machine is suitable for larger volume of fabric cutting. After assembling the fabric plies according to fabric thickness and blade height, the cutting machine is moved with the handle according to the design of marker paper which is laid on the top most fabric ply. However, occurrence of accidents is frequent with straight knife cutting machine [7]. Likewise, high speed of the machine causes high risk of damage [6]. Moreover, these cutting knives cause both the hand and leg injury to the workers during work [8]. Blade of the knife is required to be replaced to avoid these types of problems. It's suitable for straight line cutting, curve line cutting & for large part cutting. It is used for large production [6]. Apart from this machine, automated fabric cutting machine is also used in cutting section.

With the advent of numerically controlled (NC) machines in 1940s and 1950s, continuous cutting was possible. This led to greater flexibility in production as well as more economical use of materials [9]. Computerized cutting machines are used where high volume of garments is manufactured. This machine cuts fabric layers as per command given in computer system. Automation improves productivity as well as the quality of fashion products by minimizing human intervention and preventing manufacturing mistakes. Most systems in automated cutting have a similar configuration, where a cutting device is housed in a carriage that is attached to a crossbar over the cutting table. The carriage moves along the crossbar across the width of the cutting table, while the crossbar moves along the length of the table. These movements let the cutting device travel over the cutting area, and are managed precisely by a control unit. In modern cutting devices, cutting tables are equipped with a vacuum system to hold the material down and enhance cutting accuracy during the cutting process. Porous materials such as textile fabric have to be cut with an impermeable plastic cover because of this. Suction blowers usually are the component that consumes the most power in cutting operations. When multiple stacks of a fabric are spread to cut, stronger cutting power is of course required. An oscillating knife maximizes the cutting capability by moving up and down as the knife advances. The depth of oscillating stroke typically ranges from 5 millimeters (mm) to 200 mm and needs to be engineered according to the cutting conditions [9]. The use of computer involves big investment, but at the same time advantage is that it saves time, gives more opportunity, options and accuracy [10]. In the automatic fabric cutting machine, cutting is 6-8 times faster, cutting defect is negligible and accurate cutting is possible [11]. But initial investment as well as maintenance cost is high and skilled operator is also needed to operate this machine [12].

In Bangladesh, most of the garment factories use straight knife cutting machine to complete their order. But now-a-days very few factories have taken initiative to introduce computerized knife cutting machine in their cutting floor. In this

paper, a comparative study has been made between these two machines in terms of various parameters to evaluate the performance of the both machines.

2. Results

The resultant data for various parameters along with the variation have been shown using graphical representation. Here different color has been used to indicate different cutting machines. Below the graph explanation has also been mentioned.

2.1 Blade heights of the cutting machines:

Figure 1. Blade heights of the cutting machines.

In figure 1, Y-axis stands for blade height, expressed in inch and X-axis stands for cutting machine and variation of the machines. Straight knife fabric cutting machine has a blade height of 10 inch and automatic fabric cutting machine is of 8 inch. So blade height is 2 inch higher in straight knife cutting machine due to ease of movement.

2.2 Usable Blade heights of the cutting machines:

Figure 2. Usable Blade heights of the cutting machines.

Figure 2 shows that Y-axis stands for useable blade height, expressed in inch and X-axis stands for cutting machine and variation of the machines. The useable blade height for straight knife cutting machine is 70% whereas 60% for automatic fabric cutting machine. Hence useable blade height variation is 10% higher in straight knife cutting machine because of the machine size and ease of movement.

2.3 Fabric lay heights of the cutting machines:

Figure 3. Fabric lay heights of the cutting machines.

In figure 3, Y-axis exhibits the fabric lay height in inch and X-axis stands for cutting machine and variation of the machines. Fabric lay height of straight knife fabric cutting machine is almost 4-6 inch and 4-4.5 inch for automatic fabric cutting machine. So fabric lay height variation is almost 1.5 inch higher in straight knife cutting machine. The reason is the higher blade height as well as useable blade height of the cutting machine.

2.4 Fabric lay numbers of the cutting machines:

Figure 4. Fabric lay numbers of the cutting machines

Figure 4 indicates that Y-axis for fabric lay number, expressed in inch and X-axis for cutting machine and variation of the machines. Fabric lay number prepared to be cut with straight knife fabric cutting machine is 120 whereas it is 110 for automatic fabric cutting machine. Fabric lay number variation is 10 because of the ease of movement in straight knife cutting machine.

2.5 Time required for cutting operation of the cutting machines:

Figure 5. Total time required for cutting operation of the cutting machines.

Figure 5 exhibits that Y-axis stands for total time required for cutting operation, expressed in minute and X-axis stands for cutting machine and variation of the machines. Total time required for cutting one slot of spread fabric using straight knife cutting machine is 60 minutes and 20 minute for automatic fabric cutting machine. Hence the variation of time is 40 minute lesser in automatic cutting machine due to high speed and CNC system.

2.6 Wastage percentage of the cutting machines:

Figure 6. Wastage percentage of the cutting machines.

From figure 6, we see that Y-axis stands for wastage percentage in cutting machines and X-axis stands for cutting machine and variation of the machines. Straight knife cutting machine wastage is 8-10% and automatic fabric cutting machine wastage is 12-15%, so wastage is 4-5% higher in automatic machine. The in-flexible movement is the reason of higher wastage in automatic cutting machine.

2.7. Manpower required to operate the cutting machines:

Figure 7. Manpower required to operate the cutting machines.

Figure 7 evaluates the total manpower required to work in cutting machines in Y-axis stands whereas X-axis stands for cutting machine and variation of the machines. Total manpower required to work in straight knife cutting machine is 2 and in automatic fabric cutting machine it is required 3 persons. Hence one more manpower is needed to work in automatic machine where one operates the computer and two other directly operate the machine.

2.8. Efficiency of the cutting machines:

Figure 8. Efficiency of the cutting machines.

In figure 8, it is found that the efficiency of cutting machines has been shown in Y-axis whereas X-axis stands for cutting machine and variation of the machines. Efficiency of straight knife cutting machine is 70% and it is 85% for automatic fabric cutting machine, so efficiency variation is 15%. The reason of the higher efficiency is computerized method of automatic cutting machine where cutting can be accomplished with precise accuracy.

3. Discussion

From the results of various parameters of both of the cutting machines, it is observed that the automatic fabric knife cutting machine is better in overall performance. Though the percentage of using the automated machine is very lower

compared to the semi-automatic machine due to the excessive cost of the machine as well as lacking of skilled manpower for operating the machine, gradually the practice should be implemented in different industries at this golden time of industrial revolution 4.0 to cope up with the growing challenges to compete in the international market of textile industry.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1 Materials

Single jersey fabric was used as material for cutting operation. Both the straight knife cutting machine and the automatic fabric cutting machine have been used to cut the same fabric to evaluate their performance. The details of the fabric is mentioned in table 1.

Table 1. Fabric Information

Materials name	Single jersey
G.S.M	150
Yarn count	28 Ne
Composition	100% cotton
Buyer name	KIABI

4.2. Machines

4.2.1 Straight knife cutting machine

Straight knife cutting machine is the world's most popular and mostly used cutting machine. It is widely used in the garments industry of Bangladesh. The specification of the machine used for this study has been enlisted in table 2.

Table 2. Machine Specification

Machine name	Straight knife cutting machine
Brand name	KM(Mack)
Origin	Japan
Blade Size	10 Inches
Speed	1,500-3,000 RMP

4.2.2 Automatic fabric cutting machine

The second batch of single jersey fabric was cut using automatic fabric cutting machine which is equipped with CNC technology. The machine provides precise and accurate cutting. It is operated by trained technicians and supervised by highly skilled managers. The detailed specification of the machine used in this study has been mentioned in table 3.

Table 3. Machine Specification

Machine name	Automatic fabric cutting machine
Brand name	KURIS

Origin	Germany
Blade Size	8 Inch
Speed	1500-1800 rpm

5. Conclusions

In the present work we studied the significance of applying automatic cutting machines and compared with the manual cutting of fabrics in the scheme of cost and quality. Fast cutting with high accuracy and lower wastage is the most demanding requirements of the cutting section. If any mistake happens during cutting, the loss is irreversible. Hence skilled worker with efficient cutting machine is a pre-requisite for higher productivity in cutting. It is very important to cut more clothes in less time keeping pace with the increasing competition in technological development in garments production area. We can cut more fabric in less time with automatic fabric cutting machine and with a higher efficiency though the wastage is increased. On other hand, initial cost and maintenance cost is high in the automated system. Reducing time and waste is very important for any factory. However, cutting time is more in straight knife with moderate efficiency and lower wastage percentage. Reducing labor cost is suitable for large production and the labor is reduced in straight knife machine. Straight knife can easily be moved and its process is comparatively cheap. Fabric can be cut from any angle but risk is high for physical damage of operator. Hence, it could be concluded that straight knife is mostly suitable in the perspective of Bangladesh market but the automated machine should also be introduced in the factories as well to meet the demand of the fast growing market, particularly to meet the global trend of Industry 4.0.

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